

SPECIAL ISSUE: Spatial Transformation from a Planning Perspective

Establishing digital knowledge commons for regional land use governance: The case of Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler

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Abstract

Collective action is informed by what is known. In recent times, technology has substantially changed the imaginaries of sustainable futures and knowledge practices. With the rise of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), the nature of knowledge and patterns of interaction have been altered. In this article, I argue that it is necessary to take the coordinating abilities of ICT-enabled knowledge into account for collective action in regional governance processes that aim to address institutional collective action problems. To satisfy this requirement, the article explores the mediating role of ICT for collective action by conceptualising digital knowledge commons. The four coordinating abilities of digital knowledge commons are presented in the context of regional land use governance with a German case study. In the discussion, the article assesses the mediating ability of technology in the interface of knowledge and regional governance. Lastly, it opens up future research questions for the integration of digital knowledge commons in regional policy and governance.

Keywords

Digital knowledge commons; fragmented governance; collective action; land use governance; information and communication technology (ICT)

Introduction

The use of land determines the outcome of many issues related to sustainable development. As a finite resource, land plays a key role in the provision of ecosystem services that directly affect human well-being (IPCC, 2019). The importance of sustainable land use is reflected in the Sustainable Development Goals 11 (sustainable cities and communities) and 15 (life on land). In this context, the reduction of land take is a key element of both European and German sustainability and climate policies (Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz Bau und Reaktorsicherheit, 2016; European Commission, 2021). Land take is understood as the “increase over time of artificial surfaces” (Decoville & Feltgen, 2023, p. 2). It is driven by

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population growth and the corresponding need for more housing and infrastructure as well as economic development taking up land for commercial and industrial sites (Eichhorn et al., 2023). Recognizing land take as a sustainability issue, attention turned to spatial planning institutions at various levels to develop approaches to reduce land take and steer urban development (Eichhorn et al., 2023; Lacoere & Leinfelder, 2023; Schatz et al., 2021). Despite the fact that planning authority rests on the local level in Germany, the regional scale gained importance in this governance discussion based on its role as an intermediary between conflicting positions (Blotevogel et al., 2014). Next to statutory regional plans, informal planning instruments are utilised to coordinate collective action for reducing land take in the housing sector (Wahrhusen, 2022). Additionally, housing markets do not necessarily correspond with administrative boundaries but are defined by patterns of interaction characterised by relations ties which require new governance mechanisms.

Therein, I follow Krawchenko and Tomaney (2023, p. 2) in their understanding of spatial planning as the governance of land use in order to emphasise that sustainable land use planning requires attention to multi-actor and multi-scalar interactions of policies and practices that impact land use decisions. Henceforth, the governance of land use is viewed as a problem of collective action, which is characterised by fragmented authority and decision-making externalities that require inter-jurisdictional coordination. In particular the governance of land for housing development constitutes a problem of collective action, as no single municipality can solve the housing issue on its own (Bundesinstitut für Bau-, Stadt- und Raumforschung, 2024). In contrast, due to the interconnectedness of decisions, institutional collective action (ICA) dilemmas arise in which choices by one administration create spill-over effects and impact the development pathways of neighbouring jurisdictions (Feiock, 2013). Therefore, integration mechanisms are required to assimilate vertical and horizontal decision-making (Feiock, 2009).

The choice for an integration mechanism depends on the knowledge about the problem as well as on the cost and need for coordination and the associated risks. The lack or asymmetry of information has been identified as a central hinderance to coordinate collective action (Feiock, 2009; Kostka et al., 2020). With the rise of the Information Age and the development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), the nature of knowledge has been altered, and thereby the modes of communication and patterns of interaction (Potts, 2020; Soma et al., 2016). Therein technology is understood as a mediator between human experiences and practices that foster change accompanied by social innovation (Adamo & Willis, 2022; Geels, 2002). While the use of ICT in efforts to coordination sustainable land use in cities has been contemplated, little attention has been paid to the impact of ICT in the context of multi-jurisdictional governance in city-regions (Kitchin & Moore-Cherry, 2021).

Hence, this article explores the mediating abilities of ICT-enabled knowledge for coordinating collective action to address institutional collective action problems. To this end, the article develops the analytical framework of digital knowledge commons to understand how ICT-enabled knowledge enables coordination of collective action in regional land use governance. In particular, the article poses the following research question: How do digital knowledge commons enable the coordination of collective action for regional land use governance?

This article is structured as follows: Section two focuses on institutional fragmentation in functional planning spaces and reflects upon the governance of new scales to coordinate externalities of decision-making. The following section discusses the role of ICT in the interface of knowledge and governance processes focusing on knowledge commons for collective action. To deepen the understanding of ICT as a coordination mechanism for collective action, digital knowledge commons are conceptualised. Before applying the analytical framework to the case study of the regional working group Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler (:rak) in Germany, the empirical methods are introduced. The last section critically discusses the applicability of the framework in light of the debate on land use governance and provides concluding remarks on its contribution to regional policy for reducing land take in the domain of housing development.

Institutional Fragmentation in Functional Planning Spaces

Functional planning spaces are not defined by administrative boundaries but are socially constructed, based on a shared problem, relational ties, or a collective strategy aimed at achieving specific policy goals such as sustainable land use (Levin-Keitel et al., 2018, pp. 6–7). Within functional spaces, relational ties are characterised by the connectedness of service provision, policies or natural resource systems. Yet, based on the relational composition of functional spaces, decision-making authority is fragmented. Fragmentation can occur horizontally, for example, among competing local governments and vertically by overlapping federal, state or local governmental units that pursue similar or diverging policy objectives (Feiock, 2009). Central benefits of fragmentation are check and balances on power accumulation (Kitchin & Moore-Cherry, 2021) and fostering innovation through competition (Feiock, 2009). However, several formulated benefits of devolution such as an active local democracy are not substantiated with evidence (Tomaney, 2016). Moreover, research shows that fragmentation can result in inefficient organisation and decision-making that lead to a reduction in “spatial intelligence” (Kitchin & Moore-Cherry, 2021, p. 1917). Furthermore, individual decisions of governmental units can cause negative externalities that might weaken implementation efforts or even cancel each other out (Feiock, 2009). Institutional fragmentation

in functional planning spaces implies therefore that governmental units might work on an interconnected issue such as housing, yet without the appropriate communication and collaboration to configure a holistic solution. To achieve a solution in which mutual benefits arise, collective action by institutional actors is required (Feiock, 2009; Hess & Ostrom, 2007; Olson, 1971).

The Governance of Functional Planning Spaces

Most attempts to reduce institutional fragmentation with the establishment of a new scale, for example a regional government, are met with strong resistance from municipalities fearing to lose their autonomy. Hence, regional governance structures emerge to coordinate relational ties, integrate policy domains and pursue collective responses to shared problems (Rehfeld & Terstriep, 2018). Often such structures complement or arise alongside statutory planning on existing scales utilizing informal planning instruments (Smas & Schmitt, 2021) or create governance arrangements that operate on newly created scales such as city-regions or metropolitan areas (Feiock, 2009). The formation of new governance structures connects to the concept of scalar politics, which is concerned with the question for the appropriate scale to govern spatial developments (Brenner, 2009; Pütz, 2004). Therein scale is not a mere spatial reference but an “institutionalised set of practices” (Prys-Hansen et al., 2023, p. 6) in which the world is understood, policy problems are discussed and power relations are defined.

The governance of such regional scales can be understood according to Feiock (2009, 2013) with six mechanisms that deal with institutional collective action (ICA) problems (Table 1). Such mitigating institutions of regional governance vary in the degree of autonomy for the municipality (x-axis) and in the design of network relations in terms of collective or individual decision-making (y-axis) (Feiock, 2009). The favoured mechanism depends on the nature of the problem and the respective need for and cost of coordination. This article abstains from presenting each mechanism in depth and refers to the original work (Feiock, 2009, 2013) and recent advancements (Kim et al., 2022) and only presents the chosen coordination mechanism for the case study.

Table 1 - Mechanisms for Integrating Institutional Collective Action Problems (own visualisation based on Feiock, 2013, p. 404)

Encompassing Complex/ Collective	Multiplex Self-organising systems	Councils of Governments / MPOs	Regional Authorities
Intermediate / Multilateral	Working Groups	Partnerships / Multilateral ILAs	Multi-Purpose Districts
Narrow Single Issue / Bilateral	Informal Networks	Service Contracts	Single Purpose Special Districts
	Embeddedness	Contracts	Delegated Authority

Knowledge Commons in Collective Action Problems

Collective action is informed by what is known. Knowledge is a human-made resource that is derived from information, which in turn builds on available data (Hess & Ostrom, 2007). Therein knowledge relates to the struggle of interpretation within its context and its respective application whereas information can be regarded as a broader category understood as “meaningful flows of signs for a target audience” (Mol, 2009, p. 5), which builds on data that refers to numbers and figures of chosen conditions (Hess & Ostrom, 2007). With the digital age and the rise of ICT, the nature of knowledge has been altered so that scholars started to view digitally distributed information as a “shared resource by a group of people that is subject to a social dilemma” – thus a common (Hess & Ostrom, 2007, p. 3). Potts (2020, p. 273) describes ICT “a broad range of digital software and hardware that enables users to collect, share, communicate and analyse information”. Hence, ICT firstly contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the problem and secondly, it helps to reduce information asymmetry, thereby lowering the transaction costs involved in bargaining for a mutually beneficial outcome. By increasing the symmetry of information the benefits of collective action can exceed the cost (Feiock, 2009). Ultimately shared knowledge about the issue at hand impacts the cost of coordination that incentivises collective action.

By understanding knowledge as a common, I argue that knowledge shapes the selection of a governance mechanism in functional planning spaces. Hence, knowledge commons have the ability to change governance arrangements based on their linkage to power (Arts & van Tatenhove, 2004). Therein knowledge is understood as a power resource (Pütz, 2011). I therefore apply a power-sensitive understanding of the nature of knowledge (Geertman, 2006) and pay

particular attention to the interface between knowledge and governance processes (van der Molen, 2018) in the context of emerging digital technologies (Potts, 2020).

There has been ample research about the integration of ICT into the governance of cities. This includes the use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for managing and analysing spatial data, utilizing satellite imagery, sensor data or drone footage, leveraging big and open data, building digital twins for urban areas, utilising e-planning services to facilitate document sharing and streamline services for citizens and administrative tasks to develop smart cities (Batty, 2013; Hollands, 2008; Kitchin, 2014; Potts & Webb, 2023). However, Hodson and Marvin (2009) highlight that the regional scale is crucial for sustainability transformations since it acts as an intermediary between place-based efforts for change and technological innovation. To understand the role of digital technologies on the regional scale scholars have started to focus on smart regions, counties or smart territories to acknowledge the interconnected nature of cities that transcends into the utilisation of digital technologies (Garcia-Ayllon & Miralles, 2015; Matern et al., 2020; Priano et al., 2016; Wiechmann & Terfrüchte, 2017). In that smart regions are “spatially framed by digital technologies” (Matern et al., 2020, p. 2064), which require the exploration of new governance mechanisms. Kitchin and Moore-Cherry (2021) subsequently argue that too little attention has been paid to coordinating effects of digital technologies in cases of regional governance. They propose the development towards data commons as “a shared set of data tools and an aligned approach to data-driven urbanism” (Kitchin & Moore-Cherry, 2021, p. 1918). The following section conceptualises digital knowledge commons as a coordination mechanism amid institutional fragmentation in functional planning spaces. Thereby, it addresses the ways in which digital knowledge commons can inform collective action among institutional actors within regional governance.

Conceptualising Digital Knowledge Commons

With the conceptualisation of digital knowledge commons an analytical framework is created to explore the role of ICT-enabled knowledge resources in the coordination of collective action problems. The concept rests on the societal understanding presented in the Actor-Network Theory (ANT), which emphasises that society is an assemblage of people and things. As a social theory, ANT underlines the importance of technology and non-human agency in the construction of society (Latour, 2005). Therewith technology is not a mere tool, but mediates all relational ties with its presence and thus co-constructs reality so much so that “an ontological dignity [is granted] to technology” (Matthewman, 2011, p. 106). Ultimately technology can only contribute to transitions by becoming a socio-technical assemblage implying accompanying social factors like knowledge practices or changes in a socio-technical regimes (Adamo & Willis,

2022; Geels & Schot, 2007). To understand the impact and contribution of technology to societal change, its mediating abilities need to be examined within networks of human and non-human actants. Technological mediation occurs through four relations: (i) embodiment; (ii) hermeneutic; (iii) alterity; and (iv) background that shifts what we can be known about the world and what actions are derived (Adamo & Willis, 2022; Verbeek, 2021). Building onto existing literature, I derive four dimensions of digital knowledge commons.

Firstly, digital knowledge commons transform what we can know about the world. This connects to the (i) relation of embodiment and mediates the way in which the world is experienced through our senses (e.g. glasses) and how information is gathered (Adamo & Willis, 2022). Kloppenburg et al. (2022, p. 233) describe this in the context of environmental governance as a shift in the dimension of “seeing and knowing”. Digital technologies frame and impact the understanding of environmental issues in a fundamental way. Within the context of smart cities this is often described by the increased ability to collect, store and process data with ICT (Ahvenniemi et al., 2017; Bolívar & Meijer, 2016). This in turn is hoped to build up an improved evidence-base for decision-making (Jiang et al., 2021; Kitchin, 2014). Jiang et al. (2022, p. 1645) refer to “informing ICTs” that make urban governance-related knowledge available, accessible and interpretable. However, it is important to emphasise that data through which we get to know the world “do not exist independently of the ideas, techniques, technologies, people and contexts that conceive, produce, process, manage, analyse and store them” (Kitchin, 2014, p. 8). I recognise the importance of the politics of data and reject a techno-solutionist approach (Matern et al., 2020). The use of digital technologies is a socially-driven process which implies human selection and therefore in- and exclusion to frame issues (Kloppenburger et al., 2022). In that, knowledge is understood as multiple and as a co-constructive process by diverse groups of actors (Rydin, 2007). Hence, digital knowledge commons transform how knowledge about the object of interest – the city, the region, the environment – is produced, but rest on a political deliberation process within an institutional context.

Secondly, digital knowledge commons transform the ability to communicate and engage stakeholders across time and space. This dimension is connected to the academic debate of smart governance. Questioning if the introduction of ICT alone already improves knowledgeable action about the object of interest, scholars argue that the corresponding governance structure needs to be altered too (Barns, 2018; Hollands, 2008). Smart governance is regarded as organisational process that requires exploration on the acceptance and rejection of digital technologies in governance processes (Bolívar & Meijer, 2016; Jiang et al., 2022). So that the integration of ICT in governance processes enables “governments to make better decisions through the combination of ICT-based tools and collaborative governance” (Pereira et al., 2018,

p. 3). Hence, digital technologies are regarded as artefacts that embody different meanings for actors and lead to potential diverting interpretations for governance practices (Jiang et al., 2022). Thus, smart governance is socially driven and Jiang et al. (2022) as well as Adamo and Willis (2022) underline the resulting communicating abilities. Communication is facilitated by increased and optimised flows of information between different stakeholders who are horizontally and vertically fragmented. The internal and external communicating capabilities identified by Vonk (2006) work additionally towards a symmetry of information. Ruhlandt (2018) and Kloppenburg et al. (2022) emphasise that participation and engagement of stakeholders is also altered by digital technologies. Thus, assuming that governance practices become transparent, one can expect an increase in the legitimacy of decisions (Hersperger et al., 2022; Kloppenburg et al., 2022). This altered ability to communicate and engage stakeholders in governance processes relates to the (iv) background relation of technological mediation. Through the mostly unnoticed presence of digital technologies (e.g. WiFi or shared clouds), communicative practices are enabled and influenced and only disrupted when technologies fail (Verbeek, 2021). Sharing information can build trust therein reducing cost, yet the failure of shared information platform presents a risk in itself.

Thirdly, digital knowledge commons transform decision-making abilities and organisational processes. Based on the increased evidence-base due to digital technologies and the advanced processing of data, improved pattern detection and analysis are hoped to be achieved (Jiang et al., 2022). This rests on the (ii) hermeneutic relation of technological mediation which stresses that technology can symbolically represent one aspect of the world, which then requires interpretation from actors to derive actions and alter future practices (e.g. using a thermometer to decide what clothes to wear) (Verbeek, 2021). Vonk (2006) studying ICT in the context of Planning Support Systems emphasises that ICT can enable ex-ante scenario modelling to support decision-making. Increasing the amount of information through digital technologies is also viewed as a mean to increase efficiency of urban systems (Neirotti et al., 2014). Potts (2020, p. 279) speaks of “planning 3.0” as a new paradigm in which planning decisions draw on artificial intelligence to support the increasingly interconnected planning process. With advancing digitalisation of plan data, Hersperger et al. (2022, p. 2547) speak of “data-structured decision-making” that additionally alters the relationship of actors across scales due to newly available means of exchange like geoportals. However, it is important to note that newly implemented ICT-driven processes for organisational decision-making often result in path-dependencies based on related investment costs (Scholl & AlAwadhi, 2016). Furthermore, in recent years third-party vendors provided different ready-to-use solutions. Such approaches need to be critically examined to ensure that technological sovereignty and informational hegemony remain with

legitimised institutions (Hersperger et al., 2022; Scholl & AlAwadhi, 2016). Digital technologies have strategic importance for the development of cities and regions, so that purely profit oriented implementation should be questioned.

Fourthly, digital knowledge commons transform the reflection upon implementation. This implies that ex-post evaluations of decisions can be enhanced by ICT to improve future policy design (Vonk, 2006). In that the (iii) alterity relation of technology mediation is reflected. Verbeek (2021, p. 127) states that in alterity relations, technology is regarded as a “quasi-other” that can give rise to interactions and subsequently provide guidance or advice for decisions. Therein, the implementation process can be accompanied, enabling a new flexibility for management (Ruhlandt, 2018). In the context of digital plan data, this can incentivise innovation processes which allow new forms of collaboration, sense-making and knowledge distribution (Hersperger et al., 2022). Technology is thus viewed as an element of transition strategies that enables new networks (Binz & Truffer, 2011). With a systemic change in socio-technical systems, new modes of governance can arise to guide transformative processes. Focusing on ICT mediated practices Adamo and Willis (2022, p. 121844) highlight that technologies can accompany and support change in social practices understood as “interconnected constellations of embodied knowledge, mental activities, artefacts and their uses”.

Figure 1 - Four dimensions of digital knowledge commons (own visualisation)

Figure 1 displays the four dimensions and their relation to mediation theory. The conceptualisation of digital knowledge commons, employing technological mediation theory, highlights the implication that ICT-enabled knowledge resources may have for the coordination of institutional actors. This underlines the transformational character of technological mediation in generating shared meaning, alerting perception and informing new pathways for action (Verbeek, 2021). In doing so, the concept explores the spatial intelligence of regional governance mechanisms within the ICA framework of Feiock (2013) by adding a post-phenomenological perspective (Adamo & Willis, 2022; Verbeek, 2021).

Methods

The results of the article build upon seven expert interviews, four personal observations and a document analysis (n=48) in the context of a single case study (Yin, 2014). Personal interviews were held with spatial planning experts who have been involved in the regional cooperation for several years. All interviewees have expertise in spatial planning on the supra-local level. The interviews provided insight into the development process of the regional cooperation and the subsequent role of digital technologies. Moreover, each interviewee added an own perspective towards the regional cooperation given their employment in different counties or cities in the region. The interviews took place in person or digitally between February 2024 and February 2025 (Annex 1; I1-6; I13¹). With the interviewees, the development pathway of the regional cooperation was discussed as was the impact of digital technologies on planning practices and regional policy design. Moreover, the role of a common knowledge base for regional development policies was deliberated. All interviews were transcribed, and reconstructed notes were utilized to document further information.

To expand the understanding of the regional cooperation process and the development of digital technologies over the years, several documents and presentations were studied. These documents are partially publicly available on the website of the regional cooperation. Furthermore, documents that are not publicly available could be studied because of the author's involvement in the regional cooperation over the last four years. My involvement in the regional cooperation also enabled personal observations, that were conducted with the help of an ethnographic approach (Knoblauch & Vollmer, 2019). After each personal observation, a participatory protocol was created, that was guided by the previous insights of the reviewed literature on regional governance and the conceptualised digital knowledge commons.

¹ The interviews were conducted in German. Direct quotes in this article are translated by the author.

To analyse the interviews, documents and ethnographically collected data, a qualitative content analysis according to Mayring and Fenzl (2019) was deployed and executed in MaxQDA22. The software MaxQDA22 supports a qualitative content analysis that is guided by coding categories. These allow a systematic coding regime to identify patterns and derive insights. In this study, the coding categories were formed inductively and deductively. The concept of digital knowledge commons and the ICA framework informed the development of the coding categories. Through the coding guide, insights into the regional governance alongside the use of digital technologies could be gathered.

Particular attention was paid to the latest project of the regional working group called NEILA. Thereby the focus was placed on the transdisciplinary process of knowledge development for the governance of land use in the region. The understanding of NEILA, as an embedded case, is deepened with two digital questionnaires that were conducted in the year 2022 (n=11) and 2023 (n=20). The target group of the digital questionnaires were planners, politicians and administrative officials within the region. The two questionnaires contained 15 and 14 questions respectively and utilized (i) statements with which the target group could agree or disagree, (ii) closed and ordered response categories with a ranking scale from one to five and lastly (iii) provided the option to add further comments in open text boxes.

The Development of a Region

The German planning system exists in its current form for over four decades. It is a comprehensive and hierarchically structured system, which is organised in a decentralised manner and consists of four spatial levels that have varying tasks and responsibilities (Blotevogel et al., 2014; Danielzyk & Münter, 2018). Spatial planning in Germany is guided by the Federal Spatial Planning Act (ROG). Given the federal structure of Germany, the 16 federal states (*Länder*) derive their own planning acts and plans to organise spatial planning at the state and regional level. The regional level can be organized differently in each federal state (Prieb, 2018). Regional planning is tasked with the coordination of spatial development and aims to incorporate the principles of the federal state plan, provide a framework for municipal development as well as pay attention to sectoral interests and a holistic spatial development. Regional planning is hence often seen as an intermediary, moderating conflicting opinions of various stakeholders (Blotevogel et al., 2014). At the local level, municipal planning takes place, which is characterised by a far-reaching autonomy (Art. 28, para. 2 GG) that is only guided by the plans at the federal and regional planning level.

The case study region consists of the federal city of Bonn, the county of Rhein-Sieg, Ahrweiler and Neuwied. The four territorial authorities are located in two federal states – the former two in

North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW) and the latter two in Rhineland-Palatinate (RLP). Therefore, two federal state planning acts and regional plans from *Bezirksregierung Köln* (NRW) and *Planungsgemeinschaft Mittelrhein-Westerwald* (RLP) need to be taken into account. Thus, within the German planning system the region Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler is not a statutory planning space that has a formal spatial planning act or plan. Instead, it emerged because of historical developments and functional ties. As a result, informal planning instruments such as guiding principles or non-binding concepts were used to coordinate collective efforts. Informal instruments are deployed due to their adaptability and flexibility for specific situations (Danielzyk & Sondermann, 2018). Their utilisation is often problem-specific and rests on the commitment of actors rather than rule-based authority, so that the efficacy relies on the good-will and self-commitment of the actors (Blotevogel et al., 2014; Danielzyk & Sondermann, 2018). Informal planning is encouraged by the Federal Spatial Planning Act (§14 ROG) to support planning processes and implement plans. This indicates a shift in the understanding of societal steering and organisation towards a more horizontal network that engages in a deliberation about future developments (Danielzyk & Sondermann, 2018).

The deliberation process in the region Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler was ignited by the discussion to move the political capital of Germany from Bonn to Berlin. With the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989 and German reunification in 1990, the Bundestag held an intense debate in 1991, with arguments for Bonn citing its embodiment of the principles of federalism and democratic order, while Berlin was seen as the final symbolic act of German reunification (Kästner et al., 2021). Ultimately, Berlin was chosen on the 20. June 1991 as the capital by a narrow margin (338 / 320 votes). The decision was received with quite some resentment in Bonn. To balance the interests of Bonn, the Berlin-Bonn Act of 1994 established a compromise and allocated 1,4 billion Euro to the region (Paul, 2020). In paragraph six of the Berlin-Bonn act, measures for the region were defined, ensuring that Bonn would remain of national and international importance, keep seats of several ministries and upkeep functions and institutions in economic, cultural and political domains. The decision created a unique system of dual governmental seats, that is upheld until today. In January 2025, a letter of intent was signed to maintain the dual seat of government and enforce the decision of 1994.

The demarcation of the region has changed throughout the years and presents itself in three phases (Figure 2). The first phase 'Region Bonn' has been carved out in the context of the Berlin-Bonn Act in 1994. Part of this demarcation were 13 municipalities of the Rhein-Sieg county as well as four municipalities of Ahrweiler county and the city of Bonn. The composition was based on the feared consequences for the interconnected housing market (I1, I2). To counter possible negative developments, a regional housing market study was conducted in 1993, and housing

projects were initiated with federal funds explicitly marked for compensation. Within the second phase, the region grew to enclose all municipalities that belong to the county of Rhein-Sieg and Ahrweiler.

Figure 2 - The development of the regional working group (own visualisation)

Through this development, the regional working group (:rak) was established in 2001. While the first spatial demarcation (Phase I) was determined by descriptive factors, predominantly the impact for the interwoven housing market, Phase II was defined in a normative manner, focusing on the administrative boundaries of the counties (Wiechmann, 2000) and the need to establish a region with sufficient inhabitants to ensure national attention – the aim was one million inhabitants (I1). Phase III is currently in the making and is referred to as ‘Region Bundesstadt Bonn’ in the letter of intent from January 2025. This demarcation will potentially include the county of Neuwied, which has currently a visitor status in the :rak and is intended to become a full member of the regional cooperation in 2025. The amplification is motivated by the renewed discussion of compensation funds in the context of the Berlin-Bonn Act and a changed political willingness in the county itself (I5). The demarcation of the region and its cooperation is hence strongly influenced by external forces. Before the decision to move the capital to Berlin, little cooperation could be found between Bonn and its neighbouring municipalities and counties (I1).

Confronted with the prospect of a looming structural and economic crises as well as a window of opportunity, regional cooperation gained appeal. Up until today, this decision impacts the demarcation of the region as seen with the potential entry of Neuwied. The willingness to collaborate is welcomed in the region and potential learning effects are anticipated, however the functional ties towards all municipalities in the county of Neuwied is questioned alike the relations with the municipalities in the southern part of the county Ahrweiler (I3, I4).

Governing the Region Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler

The article focuses on the second phase of the regional cooperation with the regional working group Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler (:rak) that has been formalised with a treaty in 2001. Parties of the treaty are the city of Bonn, the county of Rhein-Sieg and the county of Ahrweiler. Despite being formally constituted through a treaty, participation remains voluntary for its members and all activities require their approval. Based on ethnographic observations and discussions with participants during the workshops, this voluntary nature emerged as a recurring theme. Notwithstanding active debate about alternative approaches and their respective advantages, self-commitment was consistently upheld as a core characteristic (I7, I8). The work mentality of the regional cooperation was initially delineated by administrative actors of the city of Bonn, the two counties and external experts in the wake of the Berlin/Bonn decision in 1991. With its advancement in 2006, five Rhineland rules for voluntary inter-municipal cooperation framed the jointly pursued projects. Due to discussions on a re-orientation of the regional cooperation in 2013/2014, based on critique from its members, new guiding principles were developed with all members of the regional cooperation in 2016 (Table 2).

The :rak has three institutional bodies. Firstly, the regional office (*Geschäftsstelle*) that coordinates regional activities through bi-monthly meetings. As recently as 2013, representatives of three municipalities hold permanent seats in the regional office. Before, only officials from the city of Bonn and the two counties were members. The shift resulted from demands raised by mayors who questioned the necessity of the regional cooperation and the applicableness of the results (I2). To tailor the regional actions to municipal needs and to enforce the added value for the municipalities, three permeant seats were added. As observed in situ during the research period, only two out of the three municipalities are currently represented in the regional office. Secondly, the presidency of the working group changes every two years, which is accompanied by the move of the regional office. This procedure was initiated after ten years in which the office for the regional cooperation was situated in the city of Bonn. The intention of a rotating presidency was to foster identification and ownership of the regional cooperation (I1). Therewith the :rak has no legal status, so that the administrative body at which

it resides represents the cooperation legally. Lastly, the regional plenum that consists out of the mayors of the municipalities, administration officials and visitors from the chamber of industry and commerce and other sectoral relevant actors. The plenum formulates recommendations for future actions but cannot enforce them given that no formal planning task is allocated to the :rak and the planning autonomy rests with the municipalities. The plenum works according to the unanimity principle, however since there is not a written procedure following up upon the discussed topics, the implementation seems troublesome (18). Moreover, with changing attendances of mayors or high-ranking administrative officials, the competence to even formulate recommendations has been questioned over the years (17, 18).

Table 2 - Informal Guidelines of the regional working group (own depiction based on regional documents)

Five Pillars for the future of the Region Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler (1991)	Rhineland rules for voluntary inter-municipal cooperation (2006)	The new guiding principles for the regional cooperation (2016)
1. Bonn as Federal City	1. Flexibility in the tailoring of projects	1. Actively shaping spatial structures
2. Centrum for European and International Cooperation	2. Solvable tasks	2. Planning for future generations
3. Region of future-oriented economic structure	3. Concentrated autonomy	3. Setting ecological goals
4. Region of Science and Research	4. Productive conflicts	4. Innovative region for a mobile knowledge society
5. Model for an environmentally friendly urban landscape and cultural region	5. External moderation for complex problems	5. Our special profile for Europe

The activities of the :rak are focused predominantly on the policy domain of spatial and strategic planning and aim to foster sustainable regional development by pursuing a unified approach to spatial challenges. Moreover, a focus is placed on the governance of land, taking into account the burdens and benefits that arise with the development of housing, commerce or preserving nature for individual municipalities and the whole region (Schmeer et al., 2022). Thereby the cooperation focuses on the dissemination of information, constant communication

between actors and relies on the support of external moderation and expertise, strongly leaning into the communicative side of informal planning instruments. For example, an interviewee stated that “the prophet from outside is important” for building credibility (I1). This is mirrored in several projects and studies that were conducted with the help of research institutes and private offices. Several informal plans and regional concepts are the result of utilizing informal planning procedures and instruments.

In the context of the ICA framework, the regional cooperation *:rak* can be understood as a governance mechanism to coordinate fragmented decision-making in the policy domain of spatial planning and sustainable land management. It aims to integrate strategic spatial planning decisions of 27 municipalities that are part of two counties and one county-free city in two federal states and two planning regions. In terms of institutional scope, it can be situated at the middle of the vertical axis of Feiocks’ framework. It encompasses several actors and aims to set policies in a limited field. These policies superintend the entire region, but not every actor is necessarily affected by it. The current complexity of policy fields is regarded by an interviewee as a challenge because it complicates the advancement of future integration mechanisms (I4).

Regarding the integration mechanism of Feiocks’ ICA framework, the *:rak* opted for a contractual agreement. Within the regional cooperation, the associated municipalities do not lose their planning autonomy but are bound in the name of their counties to the *:rak*. Signees of the treaty are the mayors of the city of Bonn as well as the chief administrative officer (*Landrat*) of the two counties. Of note is the fact that, although not signees, all mayors of the counties are listed as members of the working group in the treaty. Contractual agreements of this sort are characterised by a formal constitution, yet participation by its members only occurs at will and joint activities need to be approved. Therein the governance mechanism of the *:rak* rests since the start on voluntariness and the development of trust and a mutual understanding (I1, I2). Contractual agreements have medium transaction costs and imply that competition between its members still persists (Feiock, 2013). Within the regional cooperation the integration mechanism is understood as self-organised network of experts and administrative officials (I1).

In the past, projects of the regional cooperation were an impetus for two municipalities to withdraw from the *:rak*, which mirrors the defection risk that goes along with contractual agreements (Feiock, 2013). The rationale of the first withdrawal in 2010 was based on the development of a regional retail concept. The municipality of Grafschaft stated that with the development of a regional concept that includes a coordination mechanism for land use decisions on commerce, the informal character based on trust was lost. In 2018, the city of Bad Neuenahr-Ahrweiler took the regional project NEILA as a trigger to emphasise their opposition to a regional project that does not include all municipalities of the region. This was done in

consideration of the projects' aim to establish a system that balances the burdens and benefits of settlement development throughout the region (O'Neill et al., 2023; Schmeer et al., 2022).

Summing up, the regional governance mechanism of the *:rak* addresses horizontal collective action problems in the domain of spatial planning among the involved counties and respective municipalities. Also vertically, the *:rak* aims to ensure coordination among its members. This can be seen by joint statements towards the regional planning institutions to enforce the perspective of its members. Therein the *:rak* engages in §14 ROG and supports the coordination between planning levels according to the mutual feedback principle (Blotevogel et al., 2014, p. 84). Within the ICA framework, the regional governance mechanism can be understood as a multilateral interlocal agreement (Bundesinstitut für Bau-, Stadt- und Raumforschung, 2024; Feiock, 2013). However, it is worth noting that, with the rising complexity of planning, a change of opinion about the integration mechanism has become apparent (I11, I7, I8). In the questionnaire of 2022, 63 % of participants indicated a wish for a stronger binding character of intermunicipal cooperation (I11). Additionally, participants of the workshop stated that the current contractual agreement has too little leeway to meet the regional challenges (I7). One interview partner summed it up with “this voluntary nature creates access, but it is not very resilient - the big difficulty” (I1).

Developing digital knowledge commons for land use governance

Building upon the conceptual framework of digital knowledge commons, this section examines the digital technologies used in the regional cooperation. Attention is paid to the creation, mobilisation and utilisation of knowledge as well as to the coordinating abilities that contributed to the knowledge management in the region, particularly in the context of land use governance for housing development. The governance of land use involves acquiring information about the state of land, supporting decisions-making on land use (change), dealing with knowledge disputes between stakeholders and joining scientific and other knowledges to determine policy recommendations. The four dimensions of digital knowledge commons guide the empirical analysis. In Germany, the regional scale is regarded as an appropriate intermediary for the coordination and management of knowledge stocks as well as the co-production of explicit knowledge for integrating decision-making in institutional fragmentation (Blotevogel et al., 2014; Kaiser et al., 2017). Therefore, the application of digital knowledge commons in this policy domain adds to the discussion about the implementation and use of knowledge management in spatial planning.

Figure 3 - Screenshots website “umzug-nach-bonn.de” (Source: regional office, Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler)

The regional working group in Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler has since its beginning used digital technologies to spatially frame itself and manage regionally relevant knowledge for land use governance. The first digital technology employed by the regional cooperation was the website “umzug-nach-bonn.de” launched in 1993. This website is a direct consequence of the Berlin-Bonn Act from 1991 (I6). The decision to move the capital to Berlin and establish dual locations for ministries implied a structural change for the housing market. Insofar that a “change of shifts” needed to occur, which implied occupied houses by people who did not yet move, and new housing demands by people who needed to move to Bonn (I1). There was quite a hesitance from some, fearing to move to a rural and non-developed area in comparison to Berlin (I2). Thus, the intention with the website was to present all relevant housing and infrastructure information for future residents. This should showcase the potential of the region and underline a common approach to the new spatial challenge (I2). Therein a key characteristic of the website was that the presented housing stock spanned over the entire region (Phase II), neglecting administrative boundaries and including additional information like places of social and cultural infrastructure as well as public transport connections (Figure 3). One interviewee recalled the “rag rug of individual maps which hindered the perception at eye level” (I13). The website was made possible by the digital resources available in the city of Bonn (I5) and pioneers, who early on saw potential for the regional development process (I6). Moreover, the local newspaper (*General-Anzeiger*) as well as the provident banks from the counties and bigger cities were involved. This

ensured links both to real estate advertising and to banks for the purpose of securing loans. Thus, several external interests could be joined through the development of a shared map (I13).

Accordingly, the first digital technology utilised by the regional cooperation filled a concrete knowledge vacuum that emerged through the changing circumstances. By displaying the entire region (Phase II), its housing stock as well as social and technical infrastructure the self-perception of the region was altered. For the first time, all relevant information for the housing market were in one digital place and comparable. Thus, through the website not only planners' knowledge was altered but also made available for people who needed to move to the region. Therein, it altered the informational flow, transforming what was known about the region. Moreover, how people perceived the region, as well as how they were able to inform themselves about the housing market and infrastructure before making the move, was transformed.

Building on the successful adoption and use of the website, the *:rak* decided to expand its utilisation of digital technologies. The launch of a new website, "wohnregion-bonn.de" in the year 2006 marked a step toward developing the Regional Online Planning System (ROPS). This system aimed to enhance the regional information base and facilitate regional spatial policy on a broader scale. The initial step in this effort was the acquisition of aerial imagery for the entire region six years earlier. The *:rak* coordinated this initiative on behalf of the municipalities (I6), enabling, for the first time, a unified perception of the region. This shared perspective reinforced a sense of collective identity, referred to as the 'We-Region' ("*Wir-Region*"). This step aligned with the intention of developing a regional map that reflects residents' lived experiences, rather than being confined by administrative boundaries, which are often unnoticeable in daily life. The goal was to create a regional plan where residents could access relevant spatial information. Therein importing features from the first website. Thus, a key aspect was altering spatial knowledge about the region. While traditional maps emphasise administrative boundaries, residents experience the region more fluidly, particularly in contexts such as the housing market. ROPS sought to bridge this gap by offering digital maps that reflected this interconnectedness. Thus, it was designed to be an external communication instrument to function as a marketing instrument to promote the region (I6).

Internally, ROPS functioned as a communication instrument among municipal planners (I6). It aimed to improve cooperation by establishing a shared digital system for planning data and strategic planning decisions. A virtual network was seen as a key factor in fostering collaboration and hence provide new incentives for regional projects. This regional database was envisioned to standardise planning approaches and provide access for municipalities that lacked the financial resources or expertise to develop their own systems. A central feature of ROPS was the ability to interact with spatial information dynamically. Users could include or exclude relevant

planning data, zoom in for details or abstract for a broader view (I2, I5). This interactivity was crucial in supporting collaborative planning processes by visually demonstrating the interconnectedness of spatial development decisions. One interviewee described this innovation as giving the “regional data a face with a map” (I13). The digitized regional plan was intended to serve multiple functions, including (i) spatial monitoring on a regional scale, thus presenting and providing spatial orientation; and (ii) steering land use and development efforts. Within the system, land for housing developments that was based on jointly developed criteria was displayed (Figure 4). Lastly, (iii) a controlling function was envisioned. This should establish oversight and provide room for evaluation, thus fostering the ability to transform future spatial planning efforts.

Figure 4 - Screenshot from ROPS (Source: regional office, Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler)

ROPS was also understood as an instrument of informational politics, supporting the development of regional strategies and planning policies. As a tool for managing spatial information, it presented concrete land-use cases alongside relevant planning data. With an internal working space, the system was designed to allow municipalities to update information dynamically, ensuring that the database remained current and comprehensive. Despite a treaty

that was signed by the mayors of the municipalities (I5), this function was never picked up and eventually discontinued (I2, I3). Overall, with the launch of the new website and the corresponding development of ROPS, the aim was to establish a knowledge platform for regionally relevant planning topics. The overarching vision of ROPS was to standardise and integrate planning-relevant information across the region (I6). Through these functions, ROPS was designed to enhance spatial planning, foster collaboration, and strengthen regional identity, ultimately contributing to a more integrated and cooperative regional development.

Consolidating regional information required ongoing editorial work, a task undertaken by :rak. As the coordinating institution, :rak played a pivotal role in supporting municipalities by ensuring the consistency of regional data. However, with the development of the internet and mapping services, the service provided by :rak, could not keep up. So much so that the ROPS was eventually phased out. In 2018, the website was relaunched with the name “region-bonn.de”. A central driver for the relaunch was the less labour-intensive maintenance (I6). Today’s website presents the former and current projects of the region and provides insight into the role and guiding principles of the regional collaboration. It is not anymore intended as a marketing instrument for the region, but rather as a platform for professional audiences and administrative officials to inform themselves about the history of the cooperation. It does not present any concrete development projects in the region, nor does it inform about social or technical infrastructure.

Nonetheless, the idea to establish a digitally mediated overview for potential housing developments was not lost completely. Within the context of the project NEILA (“*Nachhaltige Entwicklung durch interkommunales Landmanagement*”), which was funded from 2018 to 2024 through the Federal Ministry of Education and Research, the idea gained traction once again. The research project built on the cooperative structures and experiences with digital technologies in context of the regional cooperation. The focus of the project was to develop a regional settlement concept that supports the governance of sustainable land use in the region (Schmeer et al., 2022). In addition to a paperback regional atlas, a regional web geoinformation system (webGIS) was developed as a shared workspace and spatial knowledge platform (Figure 5). A common intention with ROPS was to provide a webGIS to all municipalities that are not technically equipped or have sufficient resources.

In the first step, potentially available plots were recorded throughout the region. Potential plots were identified by examining federal monitoring systems and regional plans, as well as analysing preparatory land-use plans (Glass et al., 2022). All identified plots were digitalised within the webGIS. The planners from the 27 municipalities were additionally able to modify the shape of the plots or add relevant planning information, for example contamination. In total 2300

plots covering an area of 4600 hectares were recorded. Before the plots were assessed for their potential future land use (housing, commerce, industry), exclusion criteria like Flora and Fauna Areas were applied to restrict activities only to suitable areas (Glass et al., 2022). The criteria used to review all plots were jointly developed with planners and experts. This shared exercise took place over nearly two years and was regarded as a central aspect of the collaboration process (I12).

Figure 5 - Screenshot of the regional webGIS (own visualisation)

During this period, external experts, planners and policy makers reflected on the use and operationalisation of the criteria. By including and excluding certain criteria, the regional understanding of sustainable land use was jointly deliberated. For some however, this deliberation was perceived as too extensive, with one participant stating that “all in all, it was a lot of coordination for little yield in regard to content” (I12). Yet, the joint development of the results also increased the self-commitment and strengthened their relevance in conflicting situations (I2). In this context, the development of the catalogue of criteria for a regional land use governance approach reflected a sensitivity to the politics of data. In the end, the mayors of the region signed off on the final catalogue. Moreover, the chosen criteria for potential areas for housing were weighted (Glass et al., 2022). With that, a normative connotation rooted in the sustainable development pathway of the individual municipalities and their regional collaboration was embedded into the data. Thus, through the joint activities of the regional

working group, its affiliated municipalities, and the project NEILA, all potential settlement plots were made visible and known with regard to their potential future use. It is important to note that plots were not only assessed in terms of land use, but also with regard to the value for the regional green infrastructure and potential conflicts arising from state and regional planning objectives and principles.

The review of all potential settlement areas, along with their assessment for future development, influenced communication among planners and across different scales within the region. Through the work of the project, it became possible to see potential development plots across the entire region. However, it is questioned whether such a broad perspective is useful or whether a municipality is primarily interested in its immediate neighbours (I3). For the planners in the counties Rhein-Sieg and Ahrweiler, the regional webGIS introduced a new level of transparency, so much so that it can assist in formal planning procedures (I2). Therein, the asymmetry of information was reduced vertically as well as horizontally. Interestingly, while the planners of the region had no concerns sharing the information with the counties, they rejected the idea of sharing the identified areas with the formal regional planning institution. This illuminates the power relation that is embedded in the provision of data through digital technologies.

The webGIS was only open to planners involved in the project. The public did not have initial access to the system. It is the prerogative of the municipalities to publish the identified areas and subsequent information. Table 3 shows which municipalities took the findings to their councils or planning committees and received a resolution on how to handle them. The outcomes are by some recognised whereas other municipalities also decided to take them into consideration for future binding land-use plans. The questionnaire showed that the suspected effect of the shared concept on municipal land use planning is dependent on political recognition (I12).

Table 3 - Council decisions on project NEILA

Recognised	Recognised and taken into consideration
Bad Neuenahr-Ahrweiler (02.04.24)	Alfter (12.12.23)
Meckenheim (11.05.23)	Bonn (12.12.23)
Siegburg (11.05.23)	Königswinter (20.09.23)
Troisdorf (25.05.23)	Lohmar (01.06.23)
Ruppicheroth (05.06.24)	Sankt Augustin (28.11.23)
Adenau (22.05.23)	Swisttal (19.09.24)
	Bad Breisig (05.10.23)

In addition to assessing potential plots for settlement development, a regional density concept was jointly developed to determine the potential number of housing units for each plot (Henning et al., 2023). Contrasting the housing demand calculated by the regional planning authority with the identified settlement areas for housing and applying the regional density concept, revealed that only about 40 % of the projected housing demand can be met with current building densities (Henning et al., 2023). Planners of the region regard the regional density concept as a key aspect for future strategic development. However, they also emphasised that it may be difficult to apply in rural areas (I12). Furthermore, an excel-based tool was developed that integrated project information and enabled ex-ante scenario modelling for the region as well as for individual municipalities. Plot selection could be customized by including or excluding criteria such as the valuation of green infrastructure or potential development conflicts. In addition, the tool demonstrated how many hectares could be saved if a certain building density were applied to the selected areas

Through its use of digital technologies (webGIS), the project NEILA enabled data-structured decision-making both within individual municipalities and for the regional development process. In light of the functional connected housing market of the region, it could be shown that growing municipalities like Bonn cannot sidestep building activity into the adjacent municipalities (I4). The result showed that also those are operating close to their limits. Henceforth, a more symmetric information can serve as a basis for regional and local discussions on future housing policies. Framing local circumstances within a regional perspective was seen as a major benefit of the project (I3, I4). This regional perspective also influences planning and building activity within the municipalities. For example, in the city of Bonn, eight areas were chosen by a cross-party resolution to be examined for the development of binding land use plans. The selection of those areas rested on the information of the project and took into consideration the suggested building densities. Yet, a closer examination of the effects of the regional development concept and the webGIS on each municipality in the region seems needed to verify potential changes in planning policy and land use governance. With the establishment of the regional webGIS efforts of the past were picked up again towards the development of a shared knowledge base for the governance of land use in the region Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler. In this regard, it is not the digitalization of the plots itself that is regarded as the main advancement, but rather the shared knowledge about potential development perspectives (I2). Moreover, the process enabled a new view of settlement development potentials and through the joint catalogue of criteria and the regional density concept, highlighted the inherent interconnectedness of land use governance.

Conclusion

This article started from the problem of fragmented decision-making in functional connected planning spaces. Therein it addressed the governance of land use and in particular the housing market as a problem of collective action. Various integration mechanisms are available to moderate collaboration risk and enable collective action (Feiock, 2013). The article focused on the role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in coordinating collective efforts to reduce negative externalities from fragmented decision-making. In pursuit of this, it explored the mediating abilities of technology in the interface of knowledge and regional governance. To understand the coordinating abilities for collective action, the framework of digital knowledge commons was developed with the following dimensions: ability to (i) transform what we know about the world; (ii) transform communication and stakeholder engagement across time and space; (iii) transform decision-making abilities and organisational processes and (iv) transform our ability to reflect on implementation.

To explore what role digital knowledge commons played in the coordination of collective efforts for regional land use governance, a historical case study analysis was conducted. Empirical data was gathered through semi-structured interviews with regional planners, two digital questionnaires, ethnographic observations and document analysis. The regional cooperation in Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler (:rak) can be understood as an multilateral inter-local agreement (Feiock, 2013). Insights from current questionnaires and personal observations showed a rather divided set of opinions on the current level of authority. This relates to the associated complexity of the institutional scope and in particular the distributional issues attached to land use conflicts. With the examination of the used digital technologies by the regional working group Bonn/Rhein-Sieg/Ahrweiler through the analytical lens of digital knowledge commons, the alteration of decision costs within the integration mechanism were empirically explored.

Throughout the thirty years of regional cooperation, the :rak engaged in different aspects of digital knowledge commons to mitigate ICA dilemmas in the policy domain of housing. This started with a focus on establishing an informational level playing field for the region in 1993 by creating a website for the interconnected housing market - therein transforming what is known about the region. With the iteration of the website and the development of a regional online planning system (ROPS) in 2006, the :rak ventured into transforming communication among the planners of the region as well as starting to utilize shared knowledge as a power resource to engage into informational politics to create regional housing strategies. Despite the continuous integration and development of a shared knowledge base, the mechanism to for integrating decision-making was not altered. Instead, the established knowledge base was used in informal

planning procedures to develop planning strategies, without challenging the municipalities' planning authority. However, the empirical analysis showcased that the development of digital knowledge commons seems to require a stronger integration mechanism to ensure the continuation of a common knowledge base. Seemingly, the lack of institutional development resulted in a regression in the case of the *:rak*, as seen with the phase out of ROPS and the third iteration of the website, which only addresses external communication.

With the recent regional project NEILA, a new digital knowledge common was developed that integrated all four aspects of digital knowledge commons. Once again, the developed knowledge base contributed to the development of regional strategies and reduced cost for information searches and bargaining. Yet, once more the institutional integration mechanism has not been altered to ensure the continuation of the knowledge platform. In the end, the case study showcased that digital knowledge commons support the coordination of collective efforts for regional land use governance. However, to ensure a holistic and continuous utilisation in order to mitigate ICA dilemmas in land use governance, a socio-technical regime change seems to be necessary. In a recent interview featuring the mayor of Bonn and the head of the county Rhein-Sieg, the communication and information exchange were described as "SMS-Diplomacy" foreshadowing the timeliness of the collaboration in the digital age (General-Anzeiger, 20.06.25).

Taking on the perspective of informational governance by Mol (2006) and Soma et al. (2016), the *:rak* engaged throughout its cooperation history in governance through information with the purpose to guide and steer the land use of its municipalities. The analysis showed that digital knowledge commons spatially framed the region and therein provided a new context for local planning practice. Therein digital knowledge commons fostered internal identification for the partners of the collaboration and an echo chamber for land take decisions. Moreover, by establishing a shared knowledge platform a new regional perspective was gained. As seen in the interviews with regional planners the mentality 'them against us' was reduced by establishing a level-playing field in regard to the possibilities for housing development.

The analytical framework allows for the exploration of digital technologies in regional governance processes, therein addressing the lacking understanding of smart governance on the regional level (Ruhlandt, 2018). Moreover, it provides a perspective on the coordinating ability of digital knowledge commons for regional policy between multiple jurisdictions (Kitchin & Moore-Cherry, 2021). In that, it is important to underline that digital knowledge commons do not present a new approach to regional governance but instead serve as an analytical framework that can assist in exploring the role of ICT-enabled knowledge resources in different integration mechanisms in the context of institutional fragmentation. Therein, the article responds to the need of applying fundamental concepts of the ICA framework to shed light on changing

mechanism cost in the digital age (Kim et al., 2022). Thus, it recognises the increasing importance of informational flows in today's society (Castells, 2023; Mol, 2006) and subsequent coordinating abilities of ICT in sustainability governance (Termeer & Bruinsma, 2016) and space defining abilities of digital technologies in regions (Matern et al., 2020).

It seems relevant to integrate the developed framework with models of organisational learning to better understand single-, double- and triple-loop-learning for regional policy design as well as knowledge management in regional collaborations (Kaiser et al., 2017; McClory et al., 2017). Furthermore, a closer exploration of the effects on each municipality in the region is needed to deepen the understanding of digital knowledge commons on binding land use planning. Moreover, the development of digital knowledge commons in relation to chosen integration mechanisms in other regions should be explored to generate a comparative account (Zimmermann et al., 2023). In the studied case, digital knowledge commons supported policy coordination by enabling a joint response while maintaining the autonomy of the actors. However, it is important to critically examine in what capacity this contributes to the reduction of mechanism cost and which legitimacy implications arise from the development of a digital knowledge common for the regional governance of land use (Kim et al., 2022; Torfing et al., 2019).

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Annexes

Annex 1. List of cited interviewees, personal observations and digital questionnaires

Source Code	Specification	Date	Type of data source	Duration (min)	Recording
I1	Planner	08.10.24	Personal Interview	120	Transcription
I2	Planner	16.09.24	Personal Interview	66	Transcription
I3	Planner	18.09.24	Personal Interview	50	Transcription
I4	Planner	03.12.24	Personal Interview	38	Transcription
I5	Planner	25.10.24	Personal Interview	80	Transcription
I6	Planner	08.02.24	Phone Call	90	Transcription
I7	Workshop on development of the regional cooperation	15.11.24	Observation	180	Notes
I8	Workshop on development of the regional cooperation	10.09.24	Observation	180	Notes
I9	Focus workshop on personal and knowledge exchange	08.11.24	Observation	180	Notes
I10	Focus workshop on personal and knowledge exchange	10.12.24	Observation	90	Notes
I11	Planner / Politicians	-	Digital Questionnaire 2022	-	Digital evaluation / Notes
I12	Planner / Politicians	-	Digital Questionnaire 2023	-	Digital evaluation / Notes
I13	Planner	17.02.25	Personal Interview	120	Transcription